

Beneficial Effect of Genistein in Paclitaxel-Induced Neuropathic Pain in Albino Wistar RatsDeepa Kameswari¹, Nitya S.², Meenakshi R.³¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Aarupadai Veedu Medical College and Hospital.²Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sri Manakula Vinayagar Medical College and Hospital.³Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Nitya S

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Paclitaxel, one of the robust anticancer agents, frequently cause chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy as an adverse effect leading to dose limiting or withdrawal of the drug. Till date no effective treatment or preventive agents for chemotherapy induced neuropathic pain has shown significant clinical efficacy.

Aim: In this present study we evaluated the effect of Phytoestrogen compound Genistein against paclitaxel induced neuropathic pain in wistar rats.

Materials and Methods: The animals were divided as four groups with six animals each: Group-I: control group, Group-II: Paclitaxel only group (2 mg/kg i.p.) and Group III & IV received Genistein (10 and 20 mg/kg po) along with Paclitaxel. Paclitaxel induced pain behaviours such as cold allodynia and thermal hyperalgesia were assessed on Day 14 and Day 28 using tail immersion test, tail flick test and Eddy's hot plate.

Results: The present study showed a statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) attenuation of the paclitaxel induced decrease in latency by Genistein (20 mg/kg) in Tail flick test as well as in Eddy's hot plate compared to Paclitaxel group by Day 28.

Conclusion: Our findings suggest the beneficial role of Genistein in the treatment of Paclitaxel induced neuropathic pain.

Keywords: Chemotherapy Induced Neuropathic Pain, Genistein, Paclitaxel.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Cancer is the second most common disease causing death worldwide. The International Agency for Research on Cancer estimated about 20 million new cancer cases in the year 2022. In other words, around 1 in 5 people develop cancer in their lifetime from the disease. This global survey also predicts a 77% increase in the cancer disease burden by 2050. [1]

Chemotherapy and radiotherapy are the lifesaving management used in the cancer management. However the adverse effects produced by the cancer treatment substantially affects the quality of life. One such neurotoxic side effect is the Chemotherapy Induced Peripheral Neuropathy (CIPN). Around 68% develop CIPN within one month of chemotherapy and around 30% persist with the disabling neuropathic pain lifelong even after treatment with cancer chemotherapy. [2] The chemotherapeutic classes of drugs frequently causing CIPN includes taxanes (paclitaxel and docetaxel), vinca alkaloid antineoplastic drugs

(vincristine), platinum-based chemotherapy (cisplatin and oxaliplatin). Paclitaxel, a cytostatic drug, is known to cause CIPN in up to 50% of pediatric tumor patients mandating either dosage reduction or cessation of treatment. [3] This Paclitaxel induced peripheral neuroinflammation can be experimentally mimicked in animal models for validated preclinical research which is similar to those in human patients receiving chemotherapy. [4]

Till date no effective treatment or preventive agents for chemotherapy induced neuropathic pain has shown significant clinical efficacy. The American Association for Cancer Research suggests the drug Duloxetine for its treatment. However, duloxetine is proven less effective for paclitaxel induced CIPN. [5] Genistein, a phytoestrogen as well as a bioactive isoflavone compound, is primarily synthesized from Genista tinctoria L. The high-protein legume, Soybean, is the major source of genistein. Oestrogen has been reported to have

neuroprotective properties and to modulate pain in peripheral neuropathic pain models. [6] The Phytoestrogen novel compound Genistein has also postulated to have properties such as neuroprotection against Alzheimer's disease. [7] Also, various studies have been conducted to claim the antioxidant potential of genistein. [8] However, the therapeutic potential of genistein on chemoneuropathic pain, such as paclitaxel-induced pain has not been evaluated. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to evaluate the effect of genistein against paclitaxel induced neuropathic pain in animal model such as wistar rats.

Materials and Methods

Animals: 30 numbers adult male albino wistar rats weighing 160-230g were purchased from CPCSEA approved breeders. The animals were maintained at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with a 12-hour dark/light cycle and 50-65% humidity in the departmental animal house. They were housed in transparent cages with rice hulls as bedding material and were provided one week of acclimatization before beginning of the experiments. Rats were permitted access to water and standard rat pellet diet.

Ethical statement: Animal care and manipulations were carried out with extreme care to minimize the pain and discomfort to the animals according to the guidelines of Animal Ethics Committee of the Institute, the Committee for the Control and Supervision of Experimentation in Animals (CCSEA) and ARRIVE guidelines. Prior approval from the Institute's Animal Ethics Committee was taken before conducting the studies.

Drugs and Chemicals: Pure analytical grade powdered form of Paclitaxel and Genistein [4',5,7-Trihydroxyisoflavone, 5,7-Dihydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one] were procured from (Sigma Chemical Company, St. Louis, USA). The solutions of paclitaxel was dissolved in 2% DMSO and stored in a stock solution of 1 mg/mL. Genistein was dissolved in 0.9% NaCl.

Experimental groups: The animals were divided into four groups with a total of six animals in each group as follows:

- Group I – Control (0.9% NaCl) (5 ml/kg, p.o.)
- Group II – Paclitaxel, 2 mg/kg i.p.
- Group III - Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (10 mg/kg p.o.)
- Group IV - Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (20 mg/kg p.o.)

Induction of Paclitaxel-Induced Neuropathic Pain: Wistar rats in Groups II, III, and IV were administered single intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection of 2 mg/kg of paclitaxel on four alternate days (0, 2, 4 and 6) to give a cumulative dose of 8mg/kg. Control animals received 0.9% NaCl (5 ml/kg,

p.o.). Along with Paclitaxel, Groups III & IV received Genistein at doses of 10 mg/kg p.o. and 20 mg/kg p.o. once daily respectively, one hour after the last Paclitaxel injection, for 28 days. All the animals were tested for pain threshold using the tail immersion test, tail flick method and Eddy's hot plate tests. Nociceptive pain threshold was assessed on Day 14 and Day 28. The body weight of each of the experimental rat was noted at the beginning as well as at the end of the study. Also, the experimental rats were observed every day and all of them appeared healthy throughout the experiments according to previous established criteria. [9]

Assessment of Nociceptive Thresholds:

1. **Tail immersion test:** The test was performed by placing the rats in separate cages such that their tails hang out freely. The distal 5cm tail was immersed in ice-cold (4°C) water and duration of time taken for withdrawal of tail from cold water was noted. A cut of latency of 10 seconds was kept to avoid any injury. [10]
2. **Tail flick test:** The proximal third of the restrained rat was exposed to a point source of radiant heat by tail flick analgesiometer. The time to flick and remove the tail was noted. A cut of latency of 15 sec was kept to avoid burn injury. [11]
3. **Eddy's hot plate method:** The animals are placed on electronically heated hot plate which was maintained at $55-56^\circ\text{C}$. Time taken for response such as jumping, withdrawal and licking of paws was noted. A cut of latency of 15 sec was kept to avoid any injury. [12]

Statistical Analysis: Analysis of the data was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Software version 24. Values were expressed as the Mean \pm SEM, significance of difference between groups was further evaluated by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's (2-sided) test. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

In the present study, none of the experimental rats died during paclitaxel therapy. Paclitaxel induced pain behaviours such as cold allodynia and thermal hyperalgesia were assessed using tail immersion test, tail flick test and Eddy's hot plate. In paclitaxel-treated animals, a gradual increase in both cold allodynia (Tail immersion test) and Thermal hyperalgesia (Tail flick test and Eddy's hot plate) was noted on Day 14 and maximal on Day 28 ($P < 0.01$) in view of a significant reduction in reaction latency compared to the control group {Group I}.

The effect of Genistein on tail immersion test: Genistein (20 mg/kg) + Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg)

[Group IV] showed significant prolonged increase in the tail flicking response duration at Day14 ($p < 0.01$) compared to Paclitaxel alone treated group (Table-1). The effect of Genistein on Tail flick test and Eddy's hot plate is presented in Tables 2&3: Administration of Genistein (20mg/kg) with

Paclitaxel (Group IV) showed a statistically significant attenuation of the Paclitaxel induced decrease in latency in both tail flick test ($P < 0.01$). As well as in Eddy's hot plate ($p < 0.01$) compared to Paclitaxel group (Group II) at Day 28 (Tables 2& 3).

Table 1: Effect of Genistein in Tail Immersion Test

Group	Day 14	Day 28
Control (0.9% NaCl)	13.3 ± 1.9	12.8±1.5
Paclitaxel, 2 mg/kg i.p.	6.5±3.0*	8.2±3.1*
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (10 mg/kg p.o.)	11.0±1.4 [†]	11.0±2.8
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (20 mg/kg p.o.)	12.0 ± 2.5 ^{††}	11.3±2.0

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM. * $P < 0.01$ compared with control (0.9% NaCl) group. [†] $P < 0.05$ ^{††} $P < 0.01$ compared with Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) group.

Table 2: Effect of Genistein in Tail Flick Test

Group	Day 14	Day 28
Control (0.9% NaCl)	10.3 ± 2.9	11.3±3.0
Paclitaxel, 2 mg/kg i.p.	7.0±4.4	5.7±2.2*
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (10 mg/kg p.o.)	10.3±4.3	10.7±3.1 [†]
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (20 mg/kg p.o.)	11.7±2.4	11.7±2.2 ^{††}

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM. * $P < 0.01$ compared with control (0.9% NaCl) group. [†] $P < 0.05$ ^{††} $P < 0.01$ compared with Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) group.

Table 3: Effect of Genistein in Eddy's Hot Plate Test

Group	Day 14	Day 28
Control (0.9% NaCl)	13.0 ± 2.8	13.7±2.2
Paclitaxel, 2 mg/kg i.p.	9.3±4.1	7.0±2.8*
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (10 mg/kg p.o.)	13.3±2.1	12.2±2.7 [†]
Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) + Genistein (20 mg/kg p.o.)	10.8±2.5	12.8±2.5 ^{††}

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM. * $P < 0.01$ compared with control (0.9% NaCl) group. [†] $P < 0.05$ ^{††} $P < 0.01$ compared with Paclitaxel (2 mg/kg i.p.) group.

Discussion

Dose dependent cumulative neurotoxicity of Paclitaxel is attributed to the microtubule aggregation in dorsal root ganglion cells, axons, and Schwann cells. [13] As a consequence, peripheral neuropathy is the dose limiting toxic side effects seen in patients receiving Paclitaxel as chemotherapy, which brings the optimal anticancer management to a halt resulting in decreased quality of life. Current treatment modalities with use of anticonvulsants, antidepressants and steroids presents with limited efficacy when used for CIPN and the choice of therapeutic management is unmet. [14] The precise pathomechanism underlying paclitaxel mediated peripheral neurotoxicity is multifactorial. However, the main mechanism which has been focused extensively is the paclitaxel induced neuroinflammation via alteration of neuronal microtubulin & myelin proteins [15,16], raise in inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, glial cells and microglia [17-20], calcium dyshomeostasis [21,22], increased intracellular Reactive Oxygen Species

(ROS) [23,24] and receptors mainly TRPV-1. [25,26] Recently, novel drug discovery in the form of natural products especially, the novel plant secondary metabolite, Genistein, a dietary phytoestrogen present in soybean is on the rise for its antioxidant properties. [27] Oxidative stress is known to contribute to the development of neuropathic pain and nerve damage. Increase in the level of oxidative mediators in the peripheral neurons induced by Paclitaxel can lead to the activation of apoptotic disruption of the cell structure and impaired signal transmission, which further increase the release of inflammatory mediators. Furthermore, Paclitaxel induced pain was attributed to the raise in the levels of ROS in the neurons both in vitro and in vivo. [28] In Hypoxic-Ischaemic Brain damage induced oxidative stress in mice, Genistein showed strong antioxidant properties by suppressing reactive oxygen species such as superoxide. [29] Also, Fuloria et al highlighted the neuroprotective effect of Genistein in brain mainly by reducing oxidative stress in various studies involving memory impairment models. [30] In this study the

antinociceptive effect of Genistein was investigated using cold allodynia and thermal hyperalgesia in albino wistar rats. Findings from the current study suggest that Genistein treatment effectively mitigated the Paclitaxel induced allodynia. This is indicative of the plausible protective mechanism of action of Genistein from oxidative stress, thus preventing neurons from cell death. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first of its kind to demonstrate the effect of Genistein in paclitaxel-induced neuropathy model in rat. Similar studies have explored the potent antioxidant activity of natural compounds in protection against paclitaxel induced neuropathy in rats. [31] The limitation of the present study is that histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis to identify the pathomechanism of action of Genistein in attenuating paclitaxel induced neuropathic pain was not explored. However, the phytoestrogen Genistein is particularly promising in relieving neuropathic pain. Understanding its role may lead to development of novel therapeutic management of paclitaxel induced neurotoxicity.

Conclusion

The present study concludes a beneficial effect of Genistein by significant inhibition of paclitaxel-induced neuropathic pain in wistar albino rat model. As efforts to minimize the neurotoxicity associated with paclitaxel administration is clearly the need of the hour, further extensive research on Genistein may provide a better answer for the replication and translation of the results into the clinical setting.

References:

- Bray F, Laversanne M, Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A. Global cancer statistics 2022: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2024 Apr 4. doi: 10.3322/caac.21834. Epub ahead of print.
- Colvin LA. Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy: where are we now? *Pain*. 2019 May; 160 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):S1-S10.
- Geller JI, Wall D, Perentesis J., Blaney S. M., Bernstein M. Phase I study of paclitaxel with standard dose ifosfamide in children with refractory solid tumors: A pediatric oncology group study (POG 9376). *Pediatr. Blood Cancer* 2009; 52 (3):346–350.
- Bacalhau C, Costa-Pereira JT, Tavares I. Pre-clinical research in paclitaxel-induced neuropathic pain: a systematic review. *Front. Vet. Sci*. 2023; 10:1264668.
- Smith EM, Pang H, Cirrincione C, et al. Effect of duloxetine on pain, function, and quality of life among patients with chemotherapy-induced painful peripheral neuropathy: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2013; 309:1359–67.
- Chen Q, Zhang W, Sadana N, Chen X. Estrogen receptors in pain modulation: cellular signaling. *Biol Sex Differ*. 2021 Feb 10;12(1):22
- Duan X, Li Y, Xu F, Ding H. Study on the neuroprotective effects of Genistein on Alzheimer's disease. *Brain Behav*. 2021 May; 11(5):e02100.
- Rasheed S, Rehman K, Shahid M, Suhail S, Akash MSH. Therapeutic potentials of genistein: New insights and perspectives. *J Food Biochem*. 2022 Sep; 46(9):e14228.
- Deacon RM. Housing, husbandry and handling of rodents for behavioral experiments. *Nat Protoc*. 2006; 1(2):936-46.
- Armour WL, Smith DL. Method of determining loss of pain sensation. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 1941; 72(1):74–90.
- Na HS, Han JS, Ko KH, Hong SK. A behavioral model for peripheral neuropathy produced in rat's tail by inferior caudal trunk injury. *Neurosci Lett*. 1994 Aug 15; 177(1-2):50-2.
- Hijazi MA, El-Mallah A, Aboul-Ela M, Ellakany A. Evaluation of Analgesic Activity of Papaver libanoticum Extract in Mice: Involvement of Opioids Receptors. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2017; 2017:8935085.
- Zajączkowska R, Kocot-Kępska M, Leppert W, Wrzosek A, Mika J, Wordliczek J. Mechanisms of Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy. *Int. J. Mol. Sci*. 2019;2:1451
- Majithia N, Loprinzi CL, Smith TJ. New Practical Approaches to Chemotherapy-Induced Neuropathic Pain: Prevention, Assessment, and Treatment. *Oncology (Williston Park)*. 2016 Nov 15; 30(11):1020-29.
- Dinicola S, Fuso A, Cucina A, Santiago-Reyes M, Verna R, Unfer Vet al. Natural products—alpha-lipoic acid and acetyl-L-carnitine—in the treatment of chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy. *Eur. Rev. Med. Pharmacol. Sci*. 2018; 22:4739–4754.
- Han Y, Smith MT. Pathobiology of cancer chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) *Front. Pharmacol*. 2013; 4:156.
- Cristiano C, Avagliano C, Cuozzo M, Liguori FM, Calignano A, Russo R. The Beneficial Effects of Ultramicronized Palmitoylethanolamide in the Management of Neuropathic Pain and Associated Mood Disorders Induced by Paclitaxel in Mice. *Biomol Ther*. 2022; 12:1155
- Ma D, Wang X, Liu X, Li Z, Liu J, Cao J, et al. Macrophage Infiltration Initiates RIP3/MLKL-Dependent Necroptosis in Paclitaxel-Induced Neuropathic Pain. *Mediat Inflamm*. 2022:1–10
- Tonello R, Lee SH, Berta T. Monoclonal Anti-

- body Targeting the Matrix Metalloproteinase 9 Prevents and Reverses Paclitaxel-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy in Mice. *J Pain*. 2019; 20:515–27.
20. Zhao YX, Yao MJ, Liu Q, Xin JJ, Gao JH, Yu XC. Electroacupuncture treatment attenuates paclitaxel-induced neuropathic pain in rats via inhibiting spinal glia and the TLR4/NF- κ B pathway. *J Pain Res*. 2020; 13:239–50.
 21. Snutch TP, Zamponi GW. Recent advances in the development of T-type calcium channel blockers for pain intervention. *Br. J. Pharmacol*. 2018; 175:2375–2383.
 22. Boyette-Davis JA, Hou S, Abdi S, Dougherty PM. An updated understanding of the mechanisms involved in chemotherapy-induced neuropathy. *Pain Manag*. 2018; 8:363–375.
 23. Balkrishna A, Karumuri S, Sakat SS, Haldar S, Varshney A. Anti-oxidant profile of Divya-Peedantak-Vati abates paclitaxel-induced hyperalgesia and allodynia in CD-1 mice model of neuropathic pain. *Phytomed Plus*. 2022; 2:100229.
 24. Ilari S, Lauro F, Giancotti LA, Malafoglia V, Dagostino C, Gliozzi M et al. The protective effect of bergamot polyphenolic fraction (Bpf) on chemotherapy-induced neuropathic pain. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2021; 14:975.
 25. Wang J, Zhou F, Zhang S, Mao M, Feng S, Wang X. Participation of transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 in the analgesic effect of duloxetine for paclitaxel induced peripheral neuropathic pain. *Neurosci Lett*. 2022; 773:136512
 26. Chou PR, Lu CY, Kan JY, Wang SH, Lo JJ, Huang SH et al. Simultaneous hyperbaric oxygen therapy during systemic chemotherapy reverses chemotherapy induced peripheral neuropathy by inhibiting TLR4 and TRPV1 activation in the central and peripheral nervous system. *Support Care Cancer*. 2021; 29:6841–50.
 27. Sharifi-Rad J, Quispe C, Imran M, Rauf A, Nadeem M, Gondal TA et al. Genistein: An Integrative Overview of Its Mode of Action, Pharmacological Properties, and Health Benefits. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2021 Jul; 19:2021:3268136.
 28. Duggett NA, Griffiths LA, McKenna OE, de Santis V, Yongsanguanchai N, Mokori EB et al. Oxidative stress in the development, maintenance and resolution of paclitaxel-induced painful neuropathy. *Neuroscience*. 2016 Oct 1; 333:13-26
 29. Li Y, Zhang JJ, Chen RJ, Chen L, Chen S, Yang XF et al. Genistein mitigates oxidative stress and inflammation by regulating Nrf2/HO-1 and NF- κ B signaling pathways in hypoxic-ischemic brain damage in neonatal mice. *Ann Transl Med*. 2022 Jan; 10(2):32.
 30. Fuloria S, Yusri MAA, Sekar M, Gan SH, Rani NNIM, Lum PT et al. Genistein: A Potential Natural Lead Molecule for New Drug Design and Development for Treating Memory Impairment. *Molecules*. 2022 Jan 1; 27(1):265.
 31. Faheem M, Khan AU, Saleem MW, Shah FA, Ali F, Khan AW et al. Neuroprotective Effect of Natural Compounds in Paclitaxel-Induced Chronic Inflammatory Pain. *Molecules*. 2022 Aug 2; 27(15):4926.